

Monitoring and Strategy For Combating Floods (A Case Study of Eastern Rajasthan)

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Gopal Lal Gupta

Professor
Geography
Govt. College, Malpura,
Tonk,Rajasthan, India

Abstract

The floods are natural phenomena, they had taken place even before the men appeared on the scene and they will continue to take place in future. The man cannot control floods absolutely. One place may be protected but latter it is seen that it has been done so at the cost of other places. The question of economic availability does not allow embanking all the flood prone rivers throughout their length within a Country or even in a state, the recurring cost of maintenance will naturally add to the initial one if the embankment proposal is taken for granted, the problem will be much more complex. The protection areas may avert floods but the unprotected stretch will have a chance of getting flooded twice the normal depth. Even the area free from floods may be flooded. Since an embankment consists of the normal spill over an area, the water will either spill over a greater area or cause floods in those areas where floods are generally unexpected. Floods, being a natural phenomenon, will play their role in the natural area and every natural phenomenon has some good as well as bad effects, Floods not only bring silt as a nutrient, but they also bring sand and gravel to ruin rich agricultural land. Besides these, flood prevention has some adverse effects which have been elaborated in the chapter on Ecological imbalance/damages and losses from floods, later on, in this study.

Keywords Monitoring, Strategy, Combating Floods, Natural Phenomena.

Introduction

The immediate submission is that floods have occurred and will continue to occur. man has to control their destructive forces to minimize losses in terms of life and property. The question is how to achieve all these. The answer lies in a two fold approach because man cannot and should not stop floods only by engineering measures and at the same time he cannot be a helpless victim of them. The best way would be a combination of flood control measures and human adjustments. Man has to adjust with floods. W.R. derrick & Sewell and Gilbert F hile have suggested several possible human adjustments like accepting the loss public relief emergency action, structural changes in flood-protection, flood insurance, flood-zoning etc. Some of these are practiced in our country but some others are not relevant to our situation. People residing in a flood prone area naturally develop some sort of immunity against floods but it needs proper education, more awareness and large-scale provisions for fighting floods. Since all these need a huge amount of money, we cannot expect that they will be automatically generated. So our greater concern should be towards the human adjustment side.

Objective of study

Flood plains have been a spontaneous choice of the man for settlement through the history of the mankind in spite of the associates flood hazards. This is particularly true in deltaic and plain areas. With the rapid increase in populations, the man continues to encroach upon more and more areas in the flood plains even to the extent of using the flood channels of rivers. naturally, he has had to suffer from the imminent consequences. The mankind has been constantly fighting it. Number of flood control measures have been taken up to mitigate the fury of the flood. Paradoxically, despite the maximum efforts and money spent, losses resulting from floods are sustained not only in India but almost all over the world. The eastern Rajasthan which has also suffered from the fury of the floods is not exception to it.

Review of Literature

A running water is more responsible for sculpturing the landscape than any other surface process. Rostwedt (1968) defines flood as "A flood is any high streams flow which develops natural or artificial banks of a stream". Rodd (1968) is of the opinion that short-term rainfall characteristics such as storm size intensity and duration and channel slope rather than basin slope prone more significant which explain the incidence of floods. In India, study of floods is recognized by Rastriya Badha Ayog. Badchik (1955- 1957) Banerjee E.A.R. (1957), P.K. Sirkar (1954-1956) Mahalanobis (1927) A.S. Ramamurthi and P. Subba Rao Studied the inundation maps of Sahibi river flood of 1977 from the Remote Sensing techniques. On the floods of the Rajasthan, climatic factors, physiographic factors from various points of view relating to the floods have been studied. Shrivastav, K. N. (1943) studied the Rajputana Floods. Dr. H.S. Sharma (1973 - 76) studied the migration of rivers of Rajasthan. Sharma M.L. studied the Ghambhir river basin Rajasthan.

Main Text

The study region of the Eastern Rajasthan lies between 24°45' and 28°4' North latitude and 74°55' & 78°77' East longitude. The study region consists of Alwar, Jaipur*, Sawaimadhopur and Bharatpur** districts of the eastern Rajasthan. It has been aptly called the "Eastern Gate-Way to Rajasthan". It forms boundarie swith Gurgaon and Mahendragarh districts of Haryana in the North and the North-East, Nagaur, Jodhpur and Ajmer districts in the West, Mathura and Agra in the East. Madhya Pradesh stats in a South East, Tonk district in the South west and Kota and Bundi districts in the South. The chambal river separates the region from Madhya pradesh. Most of the tehsil boundaries are made by rivers. The region comprises the Aravallies and the Vindhyan formations. These two types of formation are separated by great boundries fault. Geological structures affects the development of drainage patterns. Almost all the area is covered with alluvium form which projects a few isolated hills of schist and quartzite belonging to Aravallis and Delhi systems. The quartz are well exposed in the Bayana hills.